

LIMITS OF SUPERSATURATION AND THE DIFFERENTIAL HEAT OF SOLUTION

BY B. S. SRIKANTAN AND M. RAMACHANDRA

Limits of supersaturation $T_s - T_c$ have been defined in terms of solubilities at T_s and T_c and the differential heat of solution has been calculated from solubility data by Van't Hoff's Isochre of T_s and T_c .

It has been shown in a previous paper (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 627) by one of us that supersolubility range follows closely the solubility curves for a number of inorganic salts in water. For substances like KCl, whose temperature coefficient of solubility is constant throughout the range, the limit $T_s - T_c$ of supersaturation is constant, and for others this is constant only in such regions where the temperature coefficient is constant. For these substances which show a metastable region in their normal solubility range, there is a considerable effect on this value of $T_s - T_c$, if the solution is heated to the metastable region before cooling. This value becomes enormous for hydrates which show a transition temperature between the hydrated and the unhydrated species of the molecules.

Taking the values for substances which belong to the first class mentioned above, it is possible to define the limits of supersaturation with reference to solubilities at two different temperatures. In Figure 1, A B is the normal solubility curve of a substance which has a low and constant temperature coefficient of solubility. A'B' is the supersaturation curve defining the metastable region beyond which spontaneous

FIG. 1

crystallisation occurs. LM is the quantity of the substance that will fall down as shown in change from T_s at N to T_c at M. Conversely, it could be concluded that a saturated solution at T_c could be rendered supersaturated at that temperature by dissolving that quantity of the substance (LM) more, which is required to saturate it at a higher temperature T_s , such that $T_s - T_c$ defines the limit of supersaturation.

Then for these substances the following thermodynamic relation holds good at normal solubility at the temperatures T_s and T_c .

These two temperatures T_s and T_c are on the normal solubility curve and hence, if $T_c = T_1$ and $T_s = T_2$ (in the absolute scale) and C_c and C_s , the solubilities at these temperatures, the equation

$$\log \frac{C_2}{C_1} = \frac{H}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right) \text{ where } C_1 \text{ and } C_2 \text{ are the solubilities}$$

at T_1 and T_2 , and $-H$ is the differential heat of solution at that saturation, i.e. for a small range of temperature, can be rewritten as

$$\log \frac{C_s}{C_c} = \frac{H}{R} \left(\frac{T_s - T_c}{T_c T_s} \right)$$

The following table gives the values for H per g. mol. of KCl calculated from the above equation at different temperatures in comparison with the data from the International Critical Tables (Vol. V, p. 169) for saturated solutions having the same ratio of solute to solvent.

$T_s - T_c$ for KCl is from the previous paper (*loc. cit.*) and is 13.1. The data from the International Critical Tables are from solubilities at 18° at different dilutions. The data in column 2 are each the average about those temperatures in column 1. As an example of method of calculation, the following outline is given.

Temperature = 40°

(i) $T_s = 273 + 40$

$T_c = 273 + 26.9$. H_1 is calculated

(ii) $T_s = 273 + 53.1$

$T_c = 273 + 40$. H_2 is calculated

The heat of solution H in column 2 = $\frac{H_1 + H_2}{2}$

TABLE I

Temp.	Calc. from equation.	H calories/g. mol.	From I.C.T.
40°	1380		1350
50°	1310		1350
70°	1330		1350
Average	1330		1350

The agreement is excellent.

Among the other substances studied in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*) NH_4Cl shows only a slight variation in the temperature coefficient of solubility. The value for the heat of solution calculated from the above equation comes out to be 1360 cal./g. mol., whereas that from the data of International Critical Tables works out as 1890 cal./g. mol. from the range from 20° to 70° . The order of concordance is fair, considering that the values for $T_s - T_c$ vary from 3.7 to 9.5 and there is stabilisation due to heating to the metastable region in the normal solubility curve.

For other substances like KNO_3 , H_3BO_3 , KClO_4 , etc., the Isochor cannot be applied since these show a marked variation in the temperature coefficient of solubility and the difference in the number of moles of solute for saturation between 20° and 80° is very high; for a small change in the value of $T_s - T_c$, the concentration change LM (Fig. 1) is great. It is possible that the ions of these salts may be highly hydrated and a small rise in temperature might remove the water molecules from the ionic sphere of the salts and act as a solvent for further solubility of the salt, and hence a steep rise in the solubility curve with temperature. In such concentrated solutions, the degree of hydration, heat capacities of the solutions, temperature and such other factors have a great influence.

The authors' best thanks are due to the Principal Dr. A. Ananthanarayana Ayer B. A., M. B. B. S., M. Sc., for his kind interest.

DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
STANLEY MEDICAL COLLEGE,
MADRAS.

Received March 3, 1951.